

IMPACT ANALYSIS OF GLASS FIBRE-REINFORCED POLYMER AND RICE STRAW ASH BONDED CONCRETE SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The retrofitting of concrete structures through Fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites as externally bonded reinforcements have become a viable strengthening technology. Considering these aspects, the current study aims to investigate the effect of the utilization of Glass fibre-reinforced polymer (GFRP) along with rice straw ash (RSA) on the impact test, i.e., drop weight test, of the concrete. Along with that, a Weibull distribution has been adopted to analyze the experimental data. The outcomes of the present study were compared with the conventional concrete and indicated that the utilization of RSA presents a viable solution for enhancing the impact resistance of concrete.

KEYWORDS

Rice Straw Ash, Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer, Weibull Distribution.

INTRODUCTION

The strength, durability, and versatility features of concrete have made it one of the most important construction materials to be used all around the world. For many centuries, it has been utilized in a variety of construction and infrastructure practices, such as roadways, bridges, buildings and many more. However, in the past few decades, a significant rise in urbanization has been observed, resulting in affecting the demand for concrete and its applications (Shafiqh et al., 2014; R. Singh & Patel, 2023; Thakur et al., 2022). With the increase in demand, the rate of consumption of these materials has also been upsurged, resulting in the consumption of massive quantities of raw materials such as fine aggregate and clinkers. A significant amount of energy and emissions in terms of CO₂ are usually involved during the processing of aforementioned materials, eventually contributing to health and environmental issues. In addition, concrete exhibits brittle behaviour and possesses high rigidity. In numerous applications, such as railway buffers, foundation pads of machinery, and shock absorbers, there is a need for enhanced energy absorption capacity and high impact resistance. In certain scenarios where the aforementioned criteria are not met, supplementary components are necessary to enhance the characteristics of concrete. Several previous studies have been carried out in the evolution of the impact resistance on fibre-based concrete (Badr et al., 2006; Zhang et al., 2014).

In recent years, researchers have been working in the field of construction and the environment in order to mitigate the problems associated with the consumption of raw materials and invent new approaches to utilize alternative materials in construction practices. It has been found that different industrial and agricultural sectors results in the formation of various by-products which have cementitious properties and could be used as binding materials along with conventional materials. Adopting this approach not only focuses on the utilization of waste materials but also influences the mechanical and durability properties of manufactured cement-based composites. Rice husk ash, metakaolin, ground blast furnace slag, fly ash, copper slag and sugarcane bagasse ash have been well-reported to increase the overall characteristics of concrete (Gastaldini et al., 2010; R. Singh et al., 2022; Sodhi et al., 2022; Sohal & Singh, 2020).

In a similar manner, rice straw ash (RSA) is an agro-industrial by-product which is originated from the biomass-based powerplants during the incineration of rice straw. In these powerplants, the heat generated by combusting rice straw is used to produce steam which further results in the generation of

electricity (Mofijur et al., 2019; R. Singh & Patel, 2022a). An enormous amount of RSA is generated due to the course of said process, creating the health and environmental problems associated with its disposal. RSA consists of a high amount of SiO₂, which has also been demonstrated to have promise for use as a cementitious material. The utilization of RSA can greatly cut down concrete's carbon footprint if used as a partial replacement for cement. In addition, the generation of RSA necessitates the combustion of rice straw, which is a renewable resource that is readily accessible in nations such as India and China (Pandey & Kumar, 2019b; R. Singh & Patel, 2022b). Considering these aspects, the incorporation of RSA in concrete can also serve as a solution for its appropriate management and enhancement in the concrete characteristics.

Along with the involvement of waste products, new technologies/methods have also been adopted during concrete production. In this context, Fiber-reinforced polymers (FRPs) have originated as one of the materials to have distinct features such as high strength-to-weight ratios, corrosion resistance, and design flexibility, making them suitable for construction purposes (Lau & Pam, 2010; Spoelstra & Monti, 1999). These composites are fabricated using thermosetting resins, such as epoxy, along with the fibres, such as carbon or glass. Glass fibre-reinforced polymer (GFRP) is one of the types of FRPs which has been widely accepted in the field of construction because of its distinct features. In this study, GFRP (Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer) was chosen over CFRP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer) due to specific reasons relevant to the research objectives. The decision to utilize GFRP was driven by factors such as cost considerations, the need for corrosion resistance, and the desired electrical insulation properties offered by GFRP (Kheyroddin et al., 2021; Mastali et al., 2016). Furthermore, GFRP's superior impact resistance characteristics made it a suitable choice for the research requirements.

Based on a comprehensive assessment of available literature, it has been noticed that being a new material, only a few studies have been carried out on the usage of RSA as a partial replacement material for concrete production. In addition to this, the combination of GFRP and RSA has not been evaluated in previous studies. Therefore, considering these research gaps, the objective of the current study is to evaluate the effect of utilization of GFRP and RSA in the concrete with a prospect to be utilization in the construction field. The proportion of RSA has been varied from 10 to 30, with an increasing interval of 10% to replace the cement content for concrete production. The GFRP has been utilized to bind the concrete using a single layer. A comparison of the RSA-based concrete prepared with and without GFRP has been made with conventional concrete. The samples were tested after 28 days of water curing. Analysis of the concrete in terms of impact resistance has been carried out. It is expected that the findings of this research will provide important light on the viability of GFRP-RSA bonded concrete systems as an environmentally friendly and high-performance substitute for conventional concrete. In addition, this study might contribute to the growing body of research on the use of alternative materials and processes in the manufacturing of concrete, which can help to lessen the negative impact that the construction industry has on human health and the environment.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This section comprises the details of the material and methods employed in order to achieve the objectives considered in the current study. A special emphasis has been given to the physical and chemical characteristics of the materials under consideration.

Cement

In the current study, “Shree” brand of Ordinary Portland cement (OPC) of grade 43, adhered to the specifications prescribed in IS 12269:1987. The specific gravity and normal consistency of OPC were 3.15 and 31%, respectively. The initial and final setting times of cement were 116 and 271 minutes.

Aggregate

The fine aggregate and coarse aggregate utilized in the concrete mix were procured from the local dealer and followed to the specifications given in IS 383:1970. The maximum size of the fine and coarse aggregate was 4.75 mm and 12.5 mm, respectively. Coarse aggregate had a fineness modulus, water absorption, moisture content, impact value and crushing value around 7, 0.8%, 0.34%, 17.4% and

16.8%, respectively. Whereas fine aggregate possesses fineness modulus, water absorption and moisture content of 3.83, 1.82% and 1.14%, respectively. Fig. 1 represents the granulometric curves of aggregate used in the current study.

Glass Fibre-Reinforced Polymer (GFRP)

GFRP used in the current study was prepared using epoxy with a ratio of 1:2 and coated on the outer surface of the samples circumferential- wise. As per the manufacturer’s report, the CSM type of GFRP had a tensile strength, elongation, and modulus around 88 MPa, 1.2%, and 7200 MPa, respectively. In addition, it had flexural modulus, strength, and elongation close to 6400 MPa, 201 MPa and 3.2%, respectively. The samples were taken out of the curing tank at a certain period of time and coated with the GFRP. After sun drying the samples coated with GFRP for 4 days, the samples were subjected to the testing procedures.

Rice Straw Ash (RSA)

The current study utilizes the RSA which was procured from Green Planet Private Limited Biomass-based Powerplant, Binjon, Nawanshahr, Punjab, India. The ash was collected in the bags and transferred to the laboratory using the vehicle. Before the application of RSA in the concrete, it was subjected to the sieve in order to remove the coarse impurities. Further, the ash was transferred to the ball mill to grind it to increase its fineness. A ratio of 20:1 (mass of ball to the ash) has been used in the milling chamber. The ash was subjected to grinding for a period of 3 hours. Subsequent to the milling process, the ash was subjected to a meticulous sieving procedure utilizing a 90-micron sieve, thereby resulting in the acquisition of a finely powdered substance. The physical characteristics of RSA are illustrated in Table 1. The particle size distribution curve of RSA is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Granulometry curve of the materials used in the current study

Table 1 Physical characteristics of rice straw ash

Properties	Value
Colour	Dark grey
Appearance	Rough
Specific gravity	2.23

Superplasticizer

A water-based superplasticizer, having 40% of solids in it, has been used to increase the workability of the concrete mixes.

Mix proportions

The design mix of the concrete has been prepared using Indian Standards. Several trials were carried out to know the optimum proportions of the materials. The present study consists of seven concrete mixes, including one control mix, six RSA-based mixes with and without the usage of 1 layer of GFRP. Five samples were prepared for each curing period and each mix to assess the compressive strength and impact resistance. The table vibrator has been used to vibrate the concrete samples. The proportions of cement, coarse aggregate, fine aggregate, water, and RSA used in the current study are given in Table 2.

Table 2 Mix Proportions of the materials

Mixes	GFRP	RSA (%)	CA (Kg/m ³)	FA (Kg/m ³)	Cement (Kg/m ³)	Water (Kg/m ³)	w/c ratio	SP (%)
Mix-1	NA	0%	1045	798	398	167	0.42	0.10
Mix-2	NA	10%	1045	798	358.2	167	0.42	0.18
Mix-3	NA	20%	1045	798	318.4	167	0.42	0.20
Mix-4	NA	30%	1045	798	278.6	167	0.42	0.23
Mix-5	1 Layer	10%	1045	798	358.2	167	0.42	0.18
Mix-6	1 Layer	20%	1045	798	318.4	167	0.42	0.20
Mix-7	1 Layer	30%	1045	798	278.6	167	0.42	0.23

Analysis Employed in the current study

Compressive strength

The present study involves cylindrical specimens with a diameter of 100 mm and a height of 200 mm, in order to analyze the concrete for compression. The samples were tested for 28 days of water curing at ambient temperature. After completion of the curing period, the samples were taken out of the curing tank and tested in accordance with the Indian Standard code IS 516:1959 (BIS Committee BDC 2 guidelines). The test will be performed using a universal compression testing machine (UTM) with a capacity of 2000 KN, and the average of three samples has been considered as the representative value of the compressive strength of the concrete. For GFRP-coated samples, the samples were tested for 32 days (including 28 of water curing and extra 4 days to dry the samples).

Resistance to the impact (drop weight test):

The experimental procedure involved conducting a drop weight test on cylindrical specimens, each measuring 100 mm in diameter and 50 mm in height. A total of three specimens were utilized for each mixture. The test was conducted in accordance with the guidelines set forth by ACI Committee 544 (ACI, 2002). The primary objective of the test was to assess the energy absorption capacity of the concrete specimens. The experimental procedure involved the application of cyclic loading to the specimen at regular intervals from a specified height.

The experimental specimens, aged for a duration of 28 and 32 days underwent testing via a drop-weight impact testing apparatus available in the laboratory. The apparatus has a hammer ball weighing 4.5 kg, which is released from a height of 450 mm and allowed to fall onto a hardened steel ball measuring 65 mm in diameter. The experimental procedure involved the placement of a steel ball at the central point of the specimen, which was subsequently positioned on the base plate within the designated lugs for optimal alignment. The experimental procedure involved the repeated dropping of a hammer ball, with the subsequent recording of the number of blows (N_1) necessary to induce the initial, observable crack on the upper surface. The number of impacts, denoted as N_2 , that resulted in the initiation of fractures to the extent that the concrete fragments met the adjacent side lugs were observed. The variables N_1 and N_2 were assigned as the respective parameters for the initial and ultimate crack resistance factors.

The impact at the initial stage of the crack was calculated using the following equation (Eq. 1):

$$E_{p.dwi} = N_1 mgh \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where, P signifies the type of energy absorbed, dwi indicates the type of test (drop weight), N_1 is the appearance of the first crack, m is the mass of the hammer (4.5 kg), g is the acceleration due to gravity, and h is the drop height

In a similar manner, the impact energy at the final crack has been calculated using the following equation (Eq. 2):

$$E_{p.dwu} = N_2 mgh \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Where, N_2 is the number of blows at the final crack.

Weibull distribution assessment of drop weight test

Various mathematical probability models have been documented in previous studies for the statistical analysis of impact test data of concrete. The Weibull distribution function has been extensively employed as a statistical tool for analyzing impact test data, owing to its widespread usage in the statistical depiction data (Li et al., 2021; Nataraja et al., 1999; Sakin & Ay, 2008; Song et al., 2005).

Statistical and analytical assessment

During the analysis of a variety and large number of specimens, the implementation of statistical analysis is essential for a better understanding of the output of the manufactured product. In the current study, the frequency histograms and probability distributions corresponding to the initial and final crack have been taken into consideration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Compressive strength

The results of compressive strength of control, RSA-based concrete after 28 days of curing are presented in Fig 3.

Fig. 3 Compressive Strength of Control and RSA-based concrete

Based on the data presented in Fig. 3 it has been noticed that the addition of a large amount of RSA in the concrete has resulted in a significant reduction in the compressive strength. In addition, it has also been noticed that the control mix (Mix-1) has presented a compressive strength of around 34.07 MPa, which is 4.22%, 14.58%, and 41.40% higher than Mix-2, Mix-3 and Mix-4, respectively. The standard deviation for Mix-1, Mix-2, Mix-3 and Mix-4 was observed to be around 1.22, 1.45, 0.78 and 1.33, respectively. The reason behind the decrease in the strength could be the dilution effect caused by the

RSA particles within the mix resulting in a lesser hydration reaction and producing low strength. In contrast, another reason could be the loss of available water, which was absorbed by the fine RSA particles (Munshi et al., 2013; Pandey & Kumar, 2019a; Razak et al., 2022). The reduction in the appropriate amount of water in the mix lessens the workability and increases the amount of unreacted products, such as cement, within the mix. Similar results have been reported in the previous studies conducted on the application of agro-industrial materials in concrete as a partial replacement of cement (Munshi & Sharma, 2019; Pandey & Kumar, 2019b; R. Singh & Patel, 2022b).

Impact resistance test (drop test)

The present study investigates the impact resistance of RSA-based concrete made with and without the application of GFRP after 28 days of curing. The performance of the specimens was evaluated based on the number of blows required to produce the first visible crack (N_1) and the final failure (N_2) (Abid et al., 2020; ACI, 2002; Kheyroddin et al., 2021; Mastali et al., 2016). The results of the impact resistance test carried out on the different concrete mixes are presented in Table 3. The failure pattern of GFRP-based concrete is illustrated in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Pattern of failure of concrete without and with GFRP

As observed from Fig. 4, the outer layer of GFRP holds the concrete samples more rigidly and helps to delay its failure time and point as compared to the samples without GFRP.

Table 3 The results of Impact resistance for control, RSA-based concrete with and without GFRP

Mix Designation	Number of Blows		Average Blows		SD		COV		N2 – N1	N2 / N1	Impact Energy (J)		Average Energy	
	First Crack (N1)	Final Crack (N2)	First Crack (N1)	Final Crack (N2)	First Crack (N1)	Final Crack (N2)	COV (%) (N1)	COV (%) (N2)			First Crack	Final Crack	First Crack	Final Crack
Mix-1	50	59	52.80	60.00	2.59	2.00	4.90	3.33	7.20	1.14	992.25	1170.855	1047.82	1190.70
	56	61									1111.32	1210.545		
	51	59									1012.095	1170.855		
	55	63									1091.475	1250.235		
	52	58									1031.94	1151.01		
Mix-2	50	59	47.80	55.80	3.11	3.35	6.52	6.00	8.00	1.17	992.25	1170.855	948.59	1107.35
	47	55									932.715	1091.475		
	45	51									893.025	1012.095		
	52	59									1031.94	1170.855		
	45	55									893.025	1091.475		
Mix-3	40	47	40.80	49.00	2.95	1.87	7.23	3.82	8.20	1.20	793.8	932.715	809.68	972.41
	39	51									773.955	1012.095		
	39	48									773.955	952.56		
	46	51									912.87	1012.095		
	40	48									793.8	952.56		
Mix-4	35	40	37.80	44.00	3.83	3.87	10.14	8.80	6.20	1.16	694.575	793.8	750.14	873.18
	38	43									754.11	853.335		
	41	49									813.645	972.405		
	42	47									833.49	932.715		
	33	41									654.885	813.645		
Mix-5	77	88	71.20	85.40	4.15	2.61	5.82	3.05	14.20	1.20	1528.065	1746.36	1412.96	1694.76
	71	85									1408.995	1686.825		
	69	88									1369.305	1746.36		
	66	84									1309.77	1666.98		
	73	82									1448.685	1627.29		
Mix-6	66	72	67.60	74.20	6.80	5.02	10.07	6.77	6.60	1.10	1309.77	1428.84	1341.52	1472.50
	62	70									1230.39	1389.15		
	72	78									1428.84	1547.91		
	77	81									1528.065	1607.445		
	61	70									1210.545	1389.15		
Mix-7	64	74	64.00	70.00	4.95	5.87	7.73	8.39	6.00	1.09	1270.08	1468.53	1270.08	1389.15
	71	77									1408.995	1528.065		
	66	70									1309.77	1389.15		
	58	62									1151.01	1230.39		
	61	67									1210.545	1329.615		

From Table 3, it has been noticed that the number of blows required to observe the first crack and final crack increases as the combined application of RSA and GFRP. The difference between the total number of blows required for the appearance of the final and first crack has been found maximum in the case of a single layer of GFRP and 10% addition of RSA as compared to the other concrete mixes. Based on the data presented in Table 3, it can be concluded that the impact resistance for the first and final crack increases with the incorporation of a single layer of GFRP and a 10% addition of RSA. Similar results have been reported in the literature by various authors when working with the fibres (Lau & Pam, 2010; Mohammadi et al., 2009; Thakur et al., 2022). The drop-weight impact test for concrete conducted by ACI Committee 544 has faced considerable criticism due to the presence of substantial variations within the obtained results (Badr & Ashour, 2005; Mastali et al., 2016). In response to this issue, a modified impact test was suggested to the ACI committee, aiming to significantly enhance the reliability of the test outcomes. The implementation of the impact test in this study was conducted in accordance with the guidelines set forth by ACI Committee 544. Consequently, the observed significant scatter in the results can be attributed to the substantial variations inherent in the repeated drop-weight impact test. In addition, the confinement ratio of the GFRP has also been tabulated using equation (Eq. 3) and presented in Table 4.

$$\text{Effective Confinement Ratio: } \frac{f_l}{f_c} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

$$f_l = \frac{2E_f n t_f \varepsilon_{fe}}{D}$$

Whereas, E_f is the modulus of FRP (7200 MPa), n is the number of plies of FRP used (1), t_f is the dry thickness of each ply used (1.2 mm), ε_{fe} is the effective strain =0.019 (ACI, 2017), D is the diameter of the cylinder, f_c is the unconfined compressive strength of samples.

Table 4 Effective confinement ratio of RSA-GFRP-based specimens

Concrete Mixes	Effective Confinement Ratio
Mix-5	0.101
Mix-6	0.112
Mix-7	0.147

It has been observed from Table 4 that the confinement ratio is increased as the content of RSA in the concrete is increased.

Weibull distribution analysis of drop weight test

The Weibull distribution function is defined by its probability distribution function (PDF) (Chen et al., 2011), which can be expressed as equation (Eq. 4) as follows:

$$f(n) = \frac{\alpha}{u} \left(\frac{n}{u}\right)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\left(\frac{n}{u}\right)^\alpha} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

Where, α is the Weibull slope parameter, u is the scale variable, n is the specific value of random variable N.

The cumulative density function (CDF) is obtained by integrating the PDF and is expressed as equation (Eq. 5 and Eq. 6) as follows:

$$F_N(n) = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{n}{u}\right)^\alpha} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

$$L_N(n) = 1 - F_N(n) = e^{-\left(\frac{n}{u}\right)^\alpha} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

In addition, the following equation has been obtained by taking the logarithms on both sides of the equation and is used to verify the number of blows for first and final crack resistance. The equation (Eq. 7) for the same is given below:

$$\ln\left[\ln\left(\frac{1}{L_N}\right)\right] = \alpha \ln(n) - \alpha \ln(u) N_1 N_2 \tag{Eq. 7}$$

The observations of the impact resistance were arranged in ascending order, and the empirical survivorship functions for N_1 and N_2 are attained using the final equation (Eq. 8) that comes out to be as follows:

$$L_N = 1 - \frac{j}{s+1} \tag{Eq. 8}$$

Where, j is the number of the failure order, and s is the total number of samples.

It has been observed that a linear relationship exists between $\ln\left[\ln\left(\frac{1}{L_N}\right)\right]$ and $L_N(n)$ when applying the two-parameter Weibull distribution to analyze statistical data related to impact resistance. Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 represent the Weibull distribution of concrete mixes corresponding to the initial and final failure of samples.

Fig. 5 Weibull distribution of N1 for Control, RSA-based concrete with and without GFRP

Fig. 6 Weibull distribution of N2 for Control, RSA-based concrete with and without GFRP

Table 5 presents the regression coefficients of α and $\alpha \ln(u)$, as well as the correlation coefficient R^2 , for all concrete specimens in the context of linear regression. It is plausible to consider the application of a two-parameter Weibull distribution to the statistical distribution of N_1 and N_2 in concrete that incorporates RSA (Chen et al., 2011; Gupta et al., 2015).

Table 5 Linear regression coefficients of impact resistance of concrete samples in Weibull distribution

Failure crack blow	Concrete mixes	RSA Content (%)	GFRP	Regression coefficient (α)	Regression coefficient ($\alpha \ln u$)	Correlation coefficient (R^2)
N1	Mix-1	0	NA	17.379	69.37	0.915
N1	Mix-2	10	NA	12.78	49.811	0.865
N1	Mix-3	20	NA	9.79	36.77	0.587
N1	Mix-4	30	NA	8.52	31.393	0.971
N1	Mix-5	10	1 Layer	15.073	64.73	0.975
N1	Mix-6	20	1 Layer	8.47	36.14	0.902
N1	Mix-7	30	1 Layer	11.35	47.476	0.971
N2	Mix-1	0	NA	24.73	101.74	0.8505
N2	Mix-2	10	NA	13.98	56.69	0.916
N2	Mix-3	20	NA	21.23	83.084	0.8302
N2	Mix-4	30	NA	9.71	37.211	0.9166
N2	Mix-5	10	1 Layer	28.11	125.46	0.941
N2	Mix-6	20	1 Layer	12.008	52.15	0.819
N2	Mix-7	30	1 Layer	10.437	44.77	0.9975

The data presented in Table 5 indicates that the coefficient of correlation of most of the mixes for the first and final crack is greater than 0.85. A coefficient of correlation equal to or exceeding 0.7 is deemed adequate for a model of reasonable quality (Rahmani et al., 2012). However, it has also been found that Mix 3 has obtained an R^2 of around 0.6 for the initial crack, which is significantly less than the other mixes. This could be due to human error or variation in the data obtained in the laboratory during the assessment of impact resistance. Based on Table 5, it can be concluded that the equations mentioned above can effectively be employed to depict the correlation between the count of initial cracks and the final strength of failure for RSA-based concrete with and without the usage of GFRP.

Statistical and analytical analysis

Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 indicate the normal probability curves of impact resistance during the initial and final crack.

Fig. 7 Histograms of the N_1 for specimens with and without the addition of RSA and GFRP (a) Mix-1, (b) Mix-2, (c) Mix-3, (d) Mix-4, (e) Mix-5, (f) Mix-6, and (g) Mix-7

Fig. 8 Histograms of the N_2 for specimens with and without the addition of RSA and GFRP (a) Mix-1, (b) Mix-2, (c) Mix-3, (d) Mix-4, (e) Mix-5, (f) Mix-6, and (g) Mix-7

It can be observed from Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 that the data obtained during the initial and final crack follows a nearly linear pattern (Benzaid & Mesbah, 2013; Mastali et al., 2016). The statistical analysis was performed utilizing the OriginLab computer programme, which facilitated the determination of probability distributions pertaining to the initial and final crack. The normality of the data was assessed through the utilization of Weibull distribution and a score method of Blom with a confidence level of 95% which is employed in order to assess the distinct dataset. In order to prove the Weibull distribution, the probability distribution of the initial and final crack observed in the current study has been taken under consideration and is presented in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10, respectively. The error bar (5%) has also been plotted to indicate the data observed during the assessment of impact resistance.

Fig. 9 Probability distribution of the specimens during initial crack (N_1) for (a) Mix-1, (b) Mix-2, (c) Mix-3, (d) Mix-4, (e) Mix-5, (f) Mix-6, and (g) Mix-7

Fig. 10 Probability distribution of the specimens during final crack (N_2) for (a) Mix-1, (b) Mix-2, (c) Mix-3, (d) Mix-4, (e) Mix-5, (f) Mix-6, and (g) Mix-7

As observed from Fig. 9 and Fig. 10, the high coefficient of determination has been noticed for the appearance of initial and final cracks during the analysis of impact resistance (Mastali et al., 2016). A significant improvement in the increase in the interval difference between the first and final crack has also been noticed in the case of Mix-5, Mix-6 and Mix-7 due to the employment of GFRP.

CONCLUSION

The current investigation aimed to assess the impact resistance of concrete that incorporates biomass-based waste material, i.e., RSA, along with a single layer of GFRP through empirical experimentation. The present study investigates the feasibility of utilizing RSA in the form of a material to be used as a partial replacement for cement for concrete production. The present study investigated the effects of varying replacement levels of RSA (10%, 20%, and 30%) with and without the application of GFRP on concrete. Furthermore, a comprehensive statistical analysis was conducted in order to gain a deeper comprehension of the impact resistance. In light of this matter, a substantial experimental database was utilised for the purpose of conducting statistical and analytical analysis. The conclusions that have been drawn are based on the results of the tests and subsequent discussions are given below:

1. The enhancement of impact resistance in concrete has been observed through the substitution of cement with RSA and the application of a single layer of GFRP.
2. There has been a strong linear correlation between the number of initial blows required to produce the first crack and the eventual occurrence of failure cracks in RSA-based concrete.
3. The impact resistance data obtained by the drop weight test conforms to the two-parameter Weibull distribution function.

Additional research can be carried out in order to explore the potential of utilizing elevated levels of RSA and other industrial by-products as a replacement for cement for concrete production. In a similar

manner, fine or coarse aggregate can also be replaced using fine and coarse crumb rubber particles or coconut shell particles. An extended version of research can also be conducted on the employment of other types of impact tests, such as flexural loading and rebound test.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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